

An ethnobotanical study of medicinal plants used by traditional healers in the Satpuda region of Taloda, Nandurbar District, Maharashtra

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Abstract

Nandurbar district is dominated by the tribals and the life of the tribals is very much dependent on forests. The livelihood and health security of tribals is due to the variety of plants found in their respective parts. Tribals know the value of plants hence they adopt the sustainable use of forest resources. They always protect the diversity of plants found in their surrounding and they never cut the plants that are used in their socio religious customs. To promote the conservation of plants, tribals have involved many of the plants in their festivals and religious ceremonies.

Many tribes, both rural and urban, have been utilizing plants for food, medicine, agrochemicals, and pharmaceuticals from ancient times. There are almost 300 tribal communities in India using herbal medicines. However, ethnomedical experts have not given the tribal region of Maharashtra enough attention. For the present study Interviews with local tribal traditional practitioners are used to get knowledge of plants. The present investigation demonstrates that the plants which are employed in traditional systems are largely taken from the wild resources. Several plant species (belonging to different families) of ethnobotanical interest are reported upon enquiries from these tribal practitioners. This study therefore concludes, vital that suitable measures are needed to safeguard the traditional knowledge in a particular area with relation to medicinal plant utilization. Phytochemical analysis of the plants is required to determine their potential as medicines.

The tribals have been using plant parts in the form of paste, powder, decoction, juice, infusion and also in crude form, with other additives like honey, curd, and urine and cow milk to get relief from different ailments like diabetes, inflammations, wounds, skin diseases, headache, indigestion, urinary infections, fever, snake bites, cough, and dental problems. This study therefore concludes, it is necessary that suitability requirements are needed in order to protect the traditional

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knowledge in a particular area with reference to medicinal plant utilization. The plants need to be evaluated through phytochemical investigation to discover potentiality as drugs.

Keywords: Ethnobotanical Uses, Conservation, Medicinal plants, Satpuda.

1. Introduction:

Since ancient times, plants have been used as medicine, foods, agrochemicals, and pharmaceuticals by large number of tribes, rural and urban people. India has more than 300 tribal communities (Achour et al., 2022; Dr Amanulla Khan, 2024; Lulesa et al., 2025; Mathur & Sundaramoorthy, 2013). Traditional medical practices are an important part of the primary health care system in the developing countries like India (Alves & Rosa, 2007; Anju & Kumar, 2024; M. B. Patil & P. A. Khan, 2017; Nguyen et al., 2019). The ethnobotanical survey can bring out many different clues for the development of drugs to treat human diseases. Now a days, a trend in the study of medicinal plants and their use in traditional medicine has been drawing attention of different medical practitioners throughout the world. People have become health cautious; the physiotherapy is more safe and effective in curing ailments without any side effects (Ahmed et al., 2025; Alexiades & Sheldon, 1996; Awan et al., 2021; M. B. Patil & P. A. Khan, 2017). Ethnic groups of various regions of the world are the real custodians of nature's wealth and experts in herbal medicine (Amanulla Khan, 2026; Bekele et al., 2022; P. Pandey et al., 2022). The traditional indigenous knowledge transferred orally for centuries is fast disappearing because of the technological developments and changing culture of ethnic groups (Ishtiaq et al., 2024; A. Kumar et al., 2021). It is for this reason the study of ethnomedicine, and its restoration have been taking place. In many countries of Africa, Asia and Latin America, people depend on traditional knowledge and medicinal plants to meet some of their primary health care needs. For instance in Africa up to 80% of the population use traditional medicine for primary health care (Abdela et al., 2022; Clement et al., 2015; Jarić et al., 2024; Patil & Khan, 2017b). Likewise, many Ethiopian communities are dependent on local plant resources for medicine. Moreover, the people in ethnic tribes are averse to change the mode of their life and traditions. But this traditional medical knowledge is fast diminishing, so it is to be procured and preserved in various forms for future generations (Adams et al., 2024; Ishtiaq et al., 2024). Thus, this study aimed to ascertain the

detailed information on the use of plants and their therapeutic medical practices popular among Satpuda tribes of Nandurbar district in Maharashtra (Khairnar et al., 2018).

2. Material and Methods:

Study area:

Geographical Overview of Nandurbar District: Nandurbar district is in the north-western parts of Maharashtra. It shares borders with Dhule district in the south and southeast, Gujarat state to the west and north, and Madhya Pradesh state to the north and northeast. The Narmada River defines the district's northern boundary. The district is situated between 21°00' to 22°30' North latitude and 73°47' to 74°47' East longitude. Nandurbar district, formed after the bifurcation of Dhule district on July 1, 1998, comprises six talukas: Akkalkuwa, Akrani Mahal (Dhadgaon), Taloda, Shahada, Nandurbar, and Navapur. The district spans a geographical area of 5,034.23 square kilometers (Census 2011). Approximately 83.29% of the population resides in rural areas, with Dhadgaon taluka having the highest tribal population at 94.95% (Census 2001; Census 2011).

Fig 1: Study area (Map Shows Nandurbar District)

The information on plants was collected by interviewing the local tribal traditional practitioners (Gou et al., 2020; Govindaraj et al., 2025; Heinrich et al., 2009). The present study revealed that the plants which are used in traditional systems are mostly collected from the wild resources.

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Ethno botanical Survey: The ethnomedicinal information was collected from knowledgeable local aged people, herdsmen and local healers aged between 40 to 70 from Taloda, Akkalkuwa, Dhadgaon tehsil, Nandurbar district Maharashtra. The information on ethnomedicine was collected during July 2025 to September 2025 through interviews and discussions. The collected information includes useful plant species with local names, parts of the plant used for curing different diseases. The scientific names of plant species and their families were identified with the help of a senior taxonomist Dr. M. B. Patil of Department of Botany, JES Science College Nandurbar, Maharashtra. The data collected from different sources of ethnic community consists of some plant species whose different parts are used for curing different diseases (Ezeanyikaa et al., 2022).

3. Results and Discussion:

The present study includes some of plant species of Angiosperms belonging to different plant families. The alphabetical order of scientific names of the plants, their families, local names, diseases, parts used, mode of administration with duration and doses are furnished in the table. Local healers have good knowledge about the use of plants for curing various ailments and also believe in supernatural powers which are also a part of their healing methods. The diagnosis of different pathogens is the first step in phyto cure treatment which can be known by one's nose, ear, hands, and eyes and it is interesting (Khan et al., 2023; N. Kumar et al., 2016).

Table 01. List of Medicinal Plants with their Uses

Sr. No.	Botanical Name & family	Common / Local Name	Plant Parts used	Medicinal uses
1	<i>Abrus precatorius</i> Fabaceae	Gunja/Ratti	Leaves, Seeds/Roots	Asthama, Sorithroat skin diaease etc.
2	<i>Plumbago zeylancia</i> Plumbaginaceae	Chitrak	Root, bark and leaves	Memory power and Relief for body pain
3	<i>Aristolochia indica</i> Aristolochiaceae	Eshwari	Roots and leaves	Scorpion bite, Snake bite
4	<i>Phyllanthus niruri</i> Euphorbiaceae	Bhumi Amla	Grinded and mixed with water	Urinary infection Jaundice
5	<i>Chlorophytum borivilianum</i> Liliaceae	Safed Musli / Musali	Root Powder (Churna) Often taken with milk or honey	Weakness, Sexual Health

6	<i>Curcuma caesia</i> Zingiberaceae	Kali Haldi	Root (Rhizome)	Asthama, leprosy, cancer, gastrointestinal issues
7	<i>Gloriosa superba</i> Liliaceae	Kallavi / Kalihari	Seeds/Roots	Obstetrics, treats gout, rheumatism
8	<i>Aglaia roxburghiana</i> Meliaceae	Ragatrohida/ Rangat roda	Root, Bark, Fruit, Flowers, Seeds.	Leprosy, Blood impurities, ulcers.
9	<i>Adansonia digitata</i> Bombacaceae	Gorakh chinch/amali	Root, Bark, Fruit	Diarrhoea and dysentery, Fever
10	<i>Rauwolfia serpentina</i>	Sarpagandha	Roots	Snake bite, anxiety, insomnia, epilepsy
11	<i>Boerhavia diffusa</i> Nyctaginaceae	Punarnava/Ghetul i	Entire plants	Jaundice, All type of inflammations
12	<i>Boswellia serrata</i> Bursaceae	Salai gugal	Bark, Gum, Resins	Asthama, dysentery, diuretic and stomachic, Fever
13	<i>Buchnanian lanzan</i> Anacardiaceae	Charoli	Roots, Leaves and Fruits	Leprosy, Skin diseases and diarrhoea.
14	<i>Butea monosperma</i> Fabaceae	Palas, Palho	Flowers, Bark Gum	Diabetes, Fever, colic worms
15	<i>Caesalpinia crista</i> Caesalpiniaceae	Sagargoti	Root bark, leaves, seeds	Cough & Fever, dyspepsia, colic
16	<i>Capparis zeylanica</i> Capparidaceae	Waghati	Root barks, Fruits	Small pox, cholera, diabetes
17	<i>Careya arborea</i> Myrtaceae	Kumbhi	Bark, Flower, Fruits	Tumor, Bronchitis, dysentery,
18	<i>Cassia fistula</i> Casalpiniaceae	Bahava/Germala	Entire plant	Leprosy, Skin disease, stomach ach
19	<i>Cordia dichotoma</i> Boraginaceae	Bhokar	Fruits, Bark	Fever, Leprosy, Skin disease, stomach ach
20	<i>Curculigo orchoides</i> Amaryllidaceae	Kali Musali	Roots	Piles, Lumbag, Used as tonic,
21	<i>Dioscorea alata</i> Dioscoreaceae	Akash vel/ Yam	Tubers	Diabetes, Gonorrhoea
22	<i>Diospyros melanoxylon</i> Ebenaceae	Temru	Fruits	Mental illnesses, Nervous diseases,
23	<i>Gloriosa superba</i> Liliaceae	Kal-lavi, Agnishikha	Roots/Rhizomes	To promoting labour pain,
24	<i>Helicteres isora</i> Serculiaceae	Murud sheng	Root, Fruits	Diabetes, dysentery, Diarrhoea
25	<i>Madhuca indica</i> Sapotaceae	Mahua/Mahu	Bark, Flower and seed	Respiratory & Skin Care, Cough
26	<i>Moringa olerifera</i> Moringaceae	Shevga	Root, Leaves, Fruits	Paralysis, Neuralgia, Haemantinic
27	<i>Ocimum sanctum</i> Lamiaceae	Tulsi	Leaves, Juice of leaves	Cold and cough Asthama
28	<i>Pterocarpus marsupium</i> Fabaceae	Beeja sar	Heartwood, Bark or Stem	Anti-dibetic
29	<i>Sterculia urens</i> Serculiaceae	Bhutya	Bark, seeds and gum	constipation, healing wounds, sores, and skin infections

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Fig: 2. Parts used from the Different Plants

The tribal healers preparations are either based on single plant part or combination of parts of several plant species. The mode of ethnomedicine usage for different diseases is in several forms, such as aqueous extract, paste and oil. In addition, milk, ginger, pepper, oil, turmeric and jaggery etc. are used as ingredients in the administration of ethnomedicine. List of medicinal plants used in Nandurbar District, Maharashtra, India. Conversely, the same ethnic tribe occupying different vegetation habitats is to be studied ethno botanically. Among the 29 plants belonging to different Families, 31% are used as leaves, 21% Barks, 14% roots, 12 % Flowers, 12% Seeds and 5% Fruits are used for various diseases. The most widely sought after plant parts in the preparation of remedies in the study area are the leaves (31%) and stem barks (21%) (Patil & Khan, 2017b, 2017a).

These plant species are used for the treatment and prevention of many ailments and diseases grouped under ailment categories (Figure 3) (Abdullah et al., 2015). The main ailments in the study area were cold, cough, wound healing, urinary disorders, body pains, stomach pain, jaundice, diarrhea, kidney diseases, neural and other diseases. The largest number of medicinal plant species are available for the treatment of skin diseases, body pains and stomachache. Half of the remedies for the above ailments are taken orally, followed by external application. Generally, fresh parts of the plant is used for the preparation of medicine (Anju & Kumar, 2024; Chandra et

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al., 2023). To improve the acceptability of certain oral remedies, additives are frequently used. Most of the reported preparations in the area are drawn from a single plant; combinations are used in twelve cases. In other parts of the country, the use of mixtures of plant species in treating a particular ailment is common (Amanulla Khan et al., 2024; J. P. Pandey et al., 2025; Tibor Hianik et al., 2025).

Fig. 3. The different elements of study area grouped under different ailment categories

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